

SOLVENCY OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH CHARTERED CAPITAL

Khalikulova Shirin Utkir kizi

TSMU, PhD Doctoral Candidate

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17847955>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 04th December 2025

Accepted: 05th December 2025

Online: 06th December 2025

KEYWORDS

*financial stability, solvency,
charter capital, insurance
company.*

ABSTRACT

The article briefly highlights the role of charter capital in ensuring the financial stability of insurance organizations and its impact on their solvency. The interdependence of capital adequacy, risk management, and financial stability is analyzed.

Introduction: "The stability of an economy (the entire national economy; its significant part or an individual organization) is understood as the ability of this economy to maintain a normal state even under conditions of minor and mostly random changes occurring in its activities. The financial stability of an enterprise is a state in which the enterprise can freely manage its financial resources, effectively direct them to ensure the continuous process of production and product realization, as well as the costs associated with its expansion and renewal".

However, while in most manufacturing enterprises the management clearly knows when, to whom, and in what amount its obligations are to be paid, the term and amount of the insurer's liabilities are determined only through probabilistic criteria (factors of risk and probability apply). Therefore, in insurance activities, not only the ability to fulfill obligations but also the ability to fully meet obligations under the most unfavorable and difficult conditions for the insurer is crucial. Thus, issues of ensuring the financial stability of insurance organizations are of particular importance for the stable and successful development of the insurance business.

Experts emphasize that "the state is directly interested in the stable functioning of the country's financial system, which is why it sets certain requirements regarding the financial stability of insurance companies," including requirements for insurance reserves, own funds, and other indicators. However, among these factors, charter capital plays the most important role. Therefore, the research task consists of studying the role and impact of charter capital in increasing the solvency and financial stability of an insurance organization.

While studying the theoretical aspects of improving the financial stability of an insurance organization, we analyzed various approaches aimed at identifying its most important characteristics and their interrelationship with charter capital. In economic literature, there are two main scientific approaches to the concept of financial stability. According to the first approach, the concept of "financial stability" of an insurance

organization is used in exactly the same sense as "solvency." Proponents of the second, resource-based approach, link financial stability with the state of the financial resources of the insurance organization and emphasize that these two categories should be considered separately in identifying different characteristics of the financial condition.

For example, S.B. Lukonin provides the following definition: "The financial stability of an insurance company is its ability to maintain the existing level of solvency over a certain period of time despite internal and external negative influences." Denisova I.P. defines financial stability as "the company's potential (balance sheet-based) ability to fulfill its obligations, meaning its financial condition should be at such a level that the company has the opportunity to fulfill its obligations in full and on time throughout all contracts."

One of the important factors influencing the financial condition of an insurer is the movement of working capital (current assets). The solvency of an insurance company is determined by the amount of reserves free from obligations. "Free reserves or the solvency margin are defined as the insurer's own funds not encumbered by any external liabilities."

Until recently, the concept of "charter capital" or "own funds" was not elaborated in legislation in detail; it was interpreted closer to the concept of net assets of insurance organizations in the form of a joint-stock company or the actual volume of the solvency margin.

In general, equity capital is considered as a key indicator providing a generalized measure of a company's financial stability. It reflects the scale of the company and serves as the main source for acquiring long-term assets. Depending on the chosen strategy, a certain part of equity can also be seen as a source for covering the working assets necessary for carrying out the company's charter activities. In financial analysis theory, this part is referred to as "own (net) working capital."

To ensure the solvency of an insurance company, the amount of its own funds, particularly charter capital, is required to increase proportionally as the volume of the company's operations grows (this issue is covered in detail in Chapter 3). In developing a system for assessing the financial condition of local insurance organizations, we rely on a group of indicators reflecting various aspects of the insurer's activities.

Practice shows that the financial stability of an insurance organization is becoming a matter of its survival in market conditions, because in today's unstable economic environment, bankruptcy is a likely outcome that may arise from the insurer's economic and financial activities. Under such conditions, the role and importance of analyzing the financial condition of insurance organizations increases even further. Such analysis is important for policyholders, commercial partners, banks (with insurers as their clients), as well as for the insurance organization itself and its branches.

Financial indicators are often calculated through ratios between absolute indicators or their linear combinations. Relative financial indicators are divided into two groups: distribution coefficients and coordination coefficients.

Distribution coefficients are used to determine the share of a specific financial indicator in the sum of indicators within the general group that includes it. Their change is of great importance in assessing the financial condition within the framework of sections like "Asset

Structure," "Liability Structure," and "Sources of Working Capital." Distribution coefficients are used to perform structural (vertical) analysis.

References:

1. Vaughan, E. J., Vaughan, T. M. Fundamentals of Risk and Insurance. Wiley, 2014.
2. Rejda, G. E., McNamara, M. J. Principles of Risk Management and Insurance. Pearson, 2021.
3. Skipper, H. D., Kwon, W. J. Risk Management and Insurance: Perspectives in a Global Economy. Wiley-Blackwell, 2018.
4. IAIS -- International Association of Insurance Supervisors. Insurance Core Principles (ICP). Available at: <https://www.iaisweb.org>
5. Swiss Re Institute. Global Insurance Reports and Reinsurance Studies. Available at: <https://www.swissre.com>
6. Izmaylov V. G. Metod sozdaniya optimal'noy perestrakhovochnoy programmy. // Strakhovoye delo, No.5, 2002. (Method for creating an optimal reinsurance program // Insurance Business, No.5, 2002.)

